

The background of the slide is a vibrant, colorful landscape. The top half shows a rocky, multi-colored terrain with patches of red, orange, yellow, and blue, interspersed with small pools of water. The bottom half shows a bright blue, sandy beach with a person in a red shirt walking along the shore carrying a surfboard. A large, semi-transparent purple oval is overlaid on the left side of the image, containing the text.

Transformation Action Workshop II

Milestone 3

Spatial Planning Ambitions

Technical References

Project Acronym	BioValue
Project Full Name	Biodiversity Value in Spatial Planning Leveraging Multi-Level and Transformative Change
Project ID	101060790
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Lead Partner	IST
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Contributor(s)	All partners
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Executive Summary

Despite international and European policies in place to halt biodiversity loss, the effect of multi-level, and multi-sector, direct and indirect drivers of change contribute to continuing negative trends. As biodiversity is impacted by many different sectors, the main challenge consists in balancing a wide range of interests and value systems across different political levels, negotiating different interests while ultimately seeking to improve, or at least maintain, biodiversity.

The main goal of BioValue is to safeguard and enhance biodiversity through transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development, upscaling opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions on biodiversity, in particular the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. To address this, BioValue adopts three complementary instrumental perspectives relevant to spatial planning processes: spatial planning and management instruments (SP&MI), environmental assessment instruments (EAI), and economic and financial instruments (E&FI).

The instrumental perspectives will support the structuring of the research in three case studies (in Portugal, Italy, and Germany) to explore and experiment BioValue research frameworks with stakeholders in action. The case studies will work as arenas for transformation (arenas₄transf), as 'experimental' areas of the capacity of the three instruments to create transformative change for biodiversity value enhancement. These cases represent distinct spatial planning systems and cultures, as well as for scale and biodiversity-related situations.

This report **delivers the results of the 2nd Transformation Action Workshop** (TAW) that had the objective of

understanding the contribution of the arenas₄transf for BioValue Spatial Planning Ambitions and identify possible interventions for transformative change valuing biodiversity in each of the arenas₄transf.

The TAWs are a series of spaces of collective thinking to co-create action-oriented knowledge and transformative pathways throughout the arena₄transf processes. Specific objectives of the TAWs are:

- i. Support the structure of the transformation processes of the arenas₄transf
- ii. Formulate needs and opportunities
- iii. Help co-creation and discussion among the arenas₄transf
- iv. Facilitate knowledge brokerage between the arenas₄transf
- v. Advance improvements for transformation of joint application of the three instrumental perspectives

Two more TAWs are expected to occur in months 23 (in Germany), and 30 (in Portugal).

The TAW II report constitutes BioValue Milestone 3 and it is a project public resource.

Transformation Action Workshop II

[understand the contribution of the arenas4transf for BioValue's spatial planning ambitions]

TAW II Objectives

Transformation Action Workshop II

September 2023 (month 15)

Understand the contribution of the Arenas for BioValue spatial planning ambitions

Specific objectives:

- Understand possible interventions for TC valuing biodiversity in each of the Arenas
- Explore what can be the contributions of the Arenas to the stated BioValue ambitions
- Identify possible transformative pathways

TAW II: structure of the workshop

- Three working groups, one per arena4transf
- Facilitator: Margarida

Jenny
Davide
Karla
Lia
Maria

Sofia
Matteo
Jorge
Erica
Silvia
Alessia
Carolina

Federica
Susana
Enzo
Heidi
Isabel
Cesar
Yuanzao

TAW II: structure of the workshop

duration: 2h30min

activities:

- 1: Interventions for Transformative Change (working groups) ~30min
- 2a: BioValue Spatial Planning Ambitions I (working groups) -45min (*10 minutes rest*)
- 2b: BioValue Spatial Planning Ambitions II (working groups) ~45min
- 3: Sharing results (plenary) ~15min

TAW II: structure of the workshop

Activity 1

Interventions for Transformative Change

1. Each Arena representative briefly explains the main results obtained in TAW I to the working group
2. Each participant associates each of the interventions for TC with ONE of the main results using the icons, considering the strongest relationships
3. Together in the working group, discussion of the results and identification of the most preminent interventions for TC representing arenas₄transf expected outcome

Activity 2

BioValue Spatial Planning Ambitions

1. Considering the most preminent interventions identified in Activity 1, discussion on what it means for each of the Ambitions – e.g., what the ambition means for the arena₄transf context
2. Developing of a pathway to impact specifying the arena₄transf reality and needs/expectations
- just one Ambition for this exercise

Activity 3

Sharing results

1. One representative of the working group share the results with all, following a brief discussion

TAW II: structure of the workshop

Each group had the following material:

- Maps of the arena4transf
- Expected Outcomes of the arena4transf
- Interventions & Interventions icons
- Ambitions & Ambitions Transformative Pathways
- Main aspects to follow-up from TAW I
- Summary of results of TAW I
- Pens & white paper

TAW II: structure of the workshop

MV

Observe and facilitate mainstreaming of biodiversity in rewetting as a policy option for the **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern** (MV) under the Climate Act. Consider the multi-level aspects of planning while bringing together different actors from different sectors of society in the co-creation of the desirable future of the peatlands.

MAFRA

Promote a planning system in **Mafra Municipality** focused on protecting and valuing biodiversity and natural values beyond current legislations/regulations, while recognizing the high touristic pressure. It also considers the inclusion of natural heritage, ecological structure, and green infrastructures in the next planning cycle.

FERSINA RIVER

Promote a planning system that incorporates the principles of ecological transition in the **Fersina River**, while recognizing the diversity of spatial characteristics. Also, expects to support the development of a coding system that incorporates biodiversity protection into spatial development by focusing on developing an intervention project on the Fersina River as a pilot project that integrates the implementation of biodiversity protection policies (from a multi-level perspective).

Interventions & Interventions icons:

(IPBES, 2019 - Five main interventions that can generate Transformative Change)

TAW II: structure of the workshop

- **Incentives and capacity-building**

Developing incentives and widespread capacity for environmental responsibility and eliminating perverse incentives

- **Cross-sectoral cooperation**

Reforming sectoral and segmented decision-making to promote integration across sectors and jurisdictions

- **Pre-emptive action**

Taking pre-emptive and precautionary actions in regulatory and management institutions and businesses to avoid, mitigate and remedy the deterioration of nature, and monitoring their outcomes

- **Decision-making in the context of resilience and uncertainty**

Managing for resilient social and ecological systems in the face of uncertainty and complexity, to deliver decisions that are robust in a wide range of scenarios

- **Environmental law and implementation**

Strengthening environmental laws and policies and their implementation, and the rule of law more generally

Ambitions & Ambitions Transformative Pathways:

Ambition 1: spatial planning safeguards, restores, allows recovery and enhances biodiversity.

Ambition 2: spatial planning significantly contributes to balanced and responsible consumption and production (avoiding external social and environmental costs).

Ambition 3: spatial planning significantly contributes to reducing socioeconomic inequalities.

TAW II:
structure of
the workshop

Results TAW I that structure the discussion:

Mafra Municipality – Main Concerns

TAW II: structure of the workshop

Group I:

- Food supply (Agriculture) link to local communities.
- Great concerns about water and its management.
- Increase knowledge of fauna, flora, habitats.
- Protecting the sea and its entire coastline.
- Financial instruments that influence the landscape.

Group II:

- Protect water lines and sanctions to bad use of water (monetarily)
- Creation of protect areas with high value for biodiversity.
- Increase fiscalization.
- Rural fire hazard map correction.

Group III:

- Renewable energies.
- Soil protection.
- Digital transformation (open data)
- Improve cooperation between entities.
- Ecological corridors.
- Creation of a "Eco-Farm" as an agricultural school and innovation center.
- Increase green spaces in urban areas.
- Promote a bigger awareness ecological questions.

Group IV:

- "Mafra" brand.
- Combat invasive species.
- Contain the artificialized areas.
- Biomass power plant.
- Decrease monocultures.
- Protect, clean and restore water lines.

Combine resume:

- Education / capacity-building of a sectoral entities on biodiversity and natural values.
- Blue and green areas.
- Water as a strategic asset.
- Agrifood systems

Results TAW I that structure the discussion:

Mafra Municipality – Summary of Main Aspects

TAW II: structure of the workshop

- **Intentions:** importance of understanding the different perceptions at stake, working towards change in promoting shared thinking about the importance of biodiversity for territorial development and spatial planning systems. Here the word of the day was **compromise**, not from the point of view that which one is right, but rather that all contributions are important and how we can reach a common sense.
- **Laws:** current regulations are restrictive in nature and may not be expressing, in a positive way, different policy options for spatial transformation that cope with biodiversity and nature. There is the need to overcome current practices of 'working in silos' and to promote cross-sectoral approaches.
- **Local governance:** governance systems need to promote relational approaches in order to promote cooperation and collaboration among different decision-making levels. Also needs to be more active, realistic, with more will in Biodiversity matters by adopting a model of governance to actually make the difference.
- **Awareness:** more needs to be done to raise awareness on biodiversity and nature, in order to, in a positive and informed way, consider/integrate biodiversity value in spatial planning policies and more local practices. Together with awareness we need to put a consequence that has a real impact in life of people, to start moving from words to action.
- **Valorization:** "green has no economic value or does not represent development" is a serious problem that needs to be overcome by associating natural resources with an economic, social or natural value (ecosystem services), acknowledging their value in all its dimensions. The feeling that remains is that there is a concern to preserve the "green" of all stakeholders, recognizing its value of extreme relevance to the municipality.

Results TAW I that structure the discussion: Fersina River – Main Concerns

TAW II:
structure of
the workshop

TAW II: structure of the workshop

Results TAW I that structure the discussion: Fersina River – Summary of Main Aspects

- Excessively **Artificiality** of the River, participants clearly express the need of renaturalising the river banks, understanding the necessity of risk flood protection
- The **poor Biodiversity** / Aggressive management of the spontaneous vegetation resulting in an habitat loss, asking for the creation of green corridors and fluvial parks
- The **lack of accessibility** to the river and usage for the citizens, that ask for a chance to have areas dedicated to get in closer proximity with the water and a clarification on how to interact safely with it.
- Need of an **integrated management** amongst the different bodies of governance, talks included a greater collaboration between different levels of governance (provincial and municipal) as well as the establishment of formal agreements on the protection of the river
- Water **pollution and degradation**, citizens ask for greater control over the inflows of the river to prevent pollution as well as a higher degree of control in sensitive areas where illegal dumping persists as well as other illegal activities.
- Lack of **knowledge** of the area, recognising the great historical importance, the need for knowledge and dedicated cultural areas has been expressed several times
- Need of enhancing **soft mobility** and public areas by reducing car mobility, all areas of interest underlined this aspect. Proposals have been put forward to limit private car circulation on the banks, and create public mobility alternatives to reach the more natural areas.

Results that structure the discussion:

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern – Summary of Main Aspects from Interviews

TAW II: structure of the workshop

- **Climate protection:** key topic and priority in environmental politics in Mecklenburg-West Pomerania and there are many activities and changes in policies ongoing. Biodiversity is supposed to be considered in the processes. For example, in the case of rewetting for climate protection, biodiversity benefits are supposed to be realized as well. A more multidimensional approach is needed to ensure that different objectives do not compete with each other.
- **Adaptation of institutional planning system:** there are not enough human resources in administrative bodies (e.g., planning offices) to integrate the different objectives into existing planning instruments in order to enable actual protection and conservation activities. For example, there is a discussion to include climate protection as a category in the list of priority areas. This means that in future areas can be defined particularly for climate protection in legally binding spatial plans. While this is necessary to fulfil climate objectives this includes the risk of neglecting biodiversity conservation.
- **Integration of different policies:** are proof to be difficult on the ground, e.g., combining the WFD with rewetting peatlands for climate protection. Biodiversity is an additional topic, which makes integration even more complex. The example used here is the planning of parts of the river Recknitz, where the attempt is made to combine WFD and peatland rewetting. Main challenges are small scale land ownership and subsidies for farming on drained peatland soils as well as sectoral thinking in administrative and other institutional structures.
- **Intersectoral challenges:** even within biodiversity conservation conflicts arise. The example given, was that quite unique ecosystems established on some of the drained peatlands. Rewetting would mean destroying these ecosystems in favour of other re-establishing wetland habitats.

Municipal Spatial Planning

Mafra Municipality, Portugal

<p><i>Understand INTENTIONS</i></p>	<p>a)</p>
<p><i>Enhance LAWS</i></p>	<p>a)</p> <p>b)</p>
<p><i>Promote LOCAL GOVERNANCE</i></p>	<p>b)</p> <p>a)</p>
<p><i>Rise AWARENESS</i></p>	<p>a), b)</p> <p>b)</p>
<p><i>Promote the value of green VALORISATION</i></p>	<p>b)</p> <p>b)</p>

Ambition 3: Mafra's Municipal Master Plan significantly contributes to reduced socioeconomic inequalities.

Basic need in the planning process – to *shift attention to Ecosystem Services*

Aspects	Context
Laws	Water use – implementing irrigation alternatives to prevent ecosystem loss.
Basic needs	Setting up a system of transfer of development rights ('perequação' – compensation system) to limit urban sprawl and compensate market inequalities.
Remediation measures	Satisfy necessities of poorer sectors of society (not only focus on touristic industry) in order to shift attention to ecosystem services.
Ecological Corridors	Manage sector inequalities (e.g., agricultural sector), intersectoral compensation mechanisms (e.g., incentives small scales / tax relief / tax implementation / enhancement large scale).
Production awareness	Financial compensations or/and tax reliefs to create/allocate agricultural land for highly biodiverse habitats/land on the sides of private agricultural fields.
Awareness/ organization	By incentivizing the use of non-intensive eco-compatible agricultural production, have a higher-grade product recognized on the local markets -> link to city market.
	Consortium / cooperative of farmers (sell products/acquire tools to be shared, bypassing "middle-man" mechanisms).

The Fersina, regenerating an urban river

Trento Municipality, Italy

ARTIFICIALITY	
POOR BIODIVERSITY	
LACK OF ACCESSIBILITY	
INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT	
POLLUTION AND DEGRADATION	
KNOWLEDGE	
SOFT MOBILITY	

Artificiality	<p>In relation to 'decision-making':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different scenarios to work on • Developing ideas in different temporal scenarios (more depending on peoples reactions) • Iterative process between implementation and alternative pathways
Poor biodiversity	<p>In relation to 'cross-sectoral cooperation':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect with the integrated management (public departments, stakeholders) • Stewardships (common goods)
Lack of accessibility	<p>In relation to 'cross-sectoral cooperation':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise the lack of accessibility to the water, and to the river areas – platform to the river (in terms of physical accessibility?) • Involving different stakeholders for different solutions • Cross-sectoral cooperation needed for permitting: a) access to the water (cooperation about the Law), and b) access to the river areas (some are not public ownership – cooperation about property) • Structural change to the
Integrated management	
Pollution and degradation	
Knowledge	<p>In relation to 'incentives and capacity building':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy actions with huge impact • Capacity building = create engagement -> e.g., printing pannels for explaining, spread knowledge (with interactive actions not only to spread knowledge but also to collect knowledge) • Possibility to start action right know -> actions during ther whole process • Publication of results of workshop and ask people what they expect -> updates about TAW to stakeholders and populations in order to: a) raise interest, b) collect feedback and ideas)
Soft mobility	

Reduce inequalities among residents-citizens

- ↳ Free access to citizens *but* thinking of entrance fee for tourists
- ↳ Raising money for the municipality
- ↳ Money applied in public services

Ambition 3: Fersina river developments significantly contributes to reduced socioeconomic inequalities.

Promote socio-economic COHESION

Public transportation and soft mobility

Trying to connect people from different socio-economic levels
 Sharing skills
 Mutual 'help'
 More access to jobs
 Spare of time / of money

Housing

Finding balance between regeneration of areas (suburbs) and gentrification of increasing house prices

▷ Unified and shared vision *on the entire*

1. Dealing with the whole river course not only for sports

Thinking about the whole without losing the specificity of the different parts of the river

- Different scenarios
- Different actors
- Different 'time'

2. Not only thinking about neighborhood but that all the municipality can benefit: thinking about need of the whole community

▷ Green spaces accessible also to lower-class people
(Places for integration, places for 'meeting' and interaction)

For all classes and citizens

1. Connectivity among spaces: possibility to reach places by foot or by bike
2. Free refreshment and recreation by water: accessible for everyone
3. Public places for summer refreshments
4. Providings shared-facilities

▷ Green and blue areas
Transportation
(*accessbile part of the city*)

Planning for vulnerable people:

- Lower class
- Women
- Children
- Old people

Rewetting Peatlands and Reforestation

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern Federal State, Germany

Overreaching Topic

'innersectoral' as also a main aspect for our arena

GENERAL

How to deal with value shifting? How do we take everybody's needs on board?

NOTIONS

Biodiversity as by-product of climate change mitigation?

Activity 3
Sharing results

Mafra Municipality **Main Outputs**

Basic needs in the planning process: to shift attention to ecosystem services.
Exploration of the agriculture uses, by acknowledging one of the main issues: irrigation.
How to satisfy basic needs in the agricultural system? Both in production and consumption, recognising the high touristic pressure.
Follow-up on the idea of an ecosystem services compensation mechanism.

Fersina River **Main Outputs**

Need to have a systemic view on the river in the planning process.
Broad up the groups and typologies of stakeholders to be engaged in the future.
Reflect on the issue of access to the river in all of its dimensions.
Planning with the vulnerable people at the center of the thinking process, exploring the issue of socioeconomic cohesion.

Mecklenburg-Vorpommern **Main Outputs**

What are the biodiversity values: importance to understand what are these values and from that define clear objectives to follow-up with to integrate and find synergies between CC protection and biodiversity in combination with CC mitigation.
Clear mapping of needs and expectations.
Continuous following of ongoing participatory processes.

Funded by the European union

